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Brown

ENGL 134

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A Stride Towards Excellence

“Up next to the stage, Daniela Molina!”

I eagerly stride forward as a diploma-like paper is handed to me and an audience, full of people just like me, applaud. With glistening eyes and a broadened smile, I paused on stage as the camera’s flashed and I searched the crowd for my mom. There she was, standing proud with her glossy chocolate eyes and red photo camera that captured the moments of my childhood. One being this; my third grade reclassification. A moment signifying my proficiency and ability to succeed in English, my second language.

As a young child, I always remember the ways in which my brain functioned and processed language/writing differently from my peers around me. In an instant, they would understand the words inscribed on paper or spoken out loud, whereas for myself, there was always a two-step process inside of my head. First, I would take in whatever was being said and let it sit in my mind for a second or two before ultimately having to translate that word/phrase from English to Spanish in order to better understand. The teacher’s announcement to “take out your pens and pencils,” almost automatically translated to “saca tus plumas y lápices.” In spite of this difference from my classmates, I never really thought much about it because somehow it always seemed to work out for me.

Despite the challenges I faced, I found myself excited for the English days at school and even excelling in them. Each time I would receive a perfect score on my tests or quizzes, I could

see my mom's face enlighten with happiness and joy as she'd proceed to make me take a picture with her photo camera. Unlike many of my classmates, my parents were never able to help me with any of my school work. I could see the sadness on my mom's face whenever she'd be unable to help me with assignments. With my dad being at work all day and my mom never having finished school in Mexico, it was always up to me to find my own resources and support.

By the third grade, I was placed in a "Combo Class," mixed with third and fourth grade students. In this class I along with the other third graders were challenged and given several opportunities to excel beyond the third grade curriculum, and it is because of this class that I became even more driven to succeed in English. About half way through the year, we began to read *Island of the Blue Dolphins*, a novel about a young girl who gets stranded on an island and has to work out the means to survive. I was confident that the weekly vocabulary quizzes and reading logs had prepared me well enough for this challenging and advanced read. As I flipped through the pages, my eyes quickly slid back and forth and the words flowed perfectly inside of my head. This was unusual. In prior years, because of my inexperience with English, I often found myself struggling during readings and needing to search up certain words online in order to better understand.

"Daniela, can you read the next paragraph for us?" my teacher asked as the previous student finished up reading their paragraph. For some odd reason, a thrill of excitement always rushed through my body when I would be selected to read to the class. As I read outloud, the words would slip right out of my mouth. No pauses, no stutters; I read it perfectly. I felt something I never had before; confident and empowered. At this moment, I finally acknowledged all the progress I had made in my English. It was no longer something foreign or scary to me, but rather just second hand nature now. There were no moments in which I felt like I

couldn't, because up to this point I had worked so hard and given up so much. Ms. Fetro, my teacher, later pulled me aside after class, "Give this to your parents when you get home sweetie," she softly said to me. I didn't really question it as I thought it was just another parent note, so gracefully, I skipped away.

"Que es?" my mom asked as I handed the envelope to her. "No se," I replied. She ripped the envelope open and inside was a certificate. *You are invited to the Reclassification ceremony.* After three years of being considered an ELD (English Language Development) student, I had finally proved to not only myself but also my teachers and the school that I could excel beyond what was expected from me. Thrilled and excited, I jumped up and down before my mom reached over, gave me a big hug, and congratulated me. This paper and this moment signified everything I had worked so hard for from such a young age.

On the big day, I slipped on a light pink dress along with the flower earrings I loved so greatly, and sat on the dining room chair as my mom tugged and tightened my hair back. "Sonríe!" she exclaimed as the camera flash blinded me. I had never been so excited, as this was one of my first ceremonies. I sat down tall and proud, surrounded by students who also endured the same hardships as me, but managed to overcome them. *We did that.*

Seeing my family as I walked across the stage was one of the best moments. The constant efforts they make inspire and move me to be better everyday. They have forced me to see that no matter the challenge or obstacle, there is always a path that will allow you to take strides towards excellence.